

WOMEN'S LITERATURE AS A " GENDER MASK " - TO THE QUESTION OF CONSTRUCTING A CREATIVE SUBJECT.

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Annotation. The subject of the study is such an aspect of " gender studies" as the construction of a " gender mask". It provides coverage of the controversy surrounding the term "women's literature", in order to show the shortcomings of the existing definitions and, having corrected them, formulate our own definition of this term. The relevance of the article is determined by the fact that " gender studies" is one of the most relevant types of modern scientific activity, and scientific novelty is determined by the insufficient study of the phenomenon of constructing the male "I" in female writers and the female "I" in male writers. The following conclusion is made in the work: since the attitude towards the creative woman was most often negative, one of the ways out for the writers was to hide behind a male mask. However, the woman still retained her "feminine intonation", manifested in the special specific characteristics of the " feminine text".

Key words: creativity, intonation, genre, literary chaos, feminism.

Annotatsiya Tadqiqot mavzusi "gender tadqiqotlari"ning "gender niqobi" qurilishi kabi jihatidir. Mavjud ta'riflarning kamchiliklarini ko'rsatish va ularni tuzatib, ushbu atamaga o'z ta'rifimizni shakllantirish uchun "ayollar adabiyoti" atamasi atrofidagi bahs-munozaralarni yoritishni ta'minlaydi. Maqolaning dolzarbligi "gender tadqiqotlari" zamonaviy ilmiy faoliyatning eng dolzarb turlaridan biri ekanligi bilan belgilanadi va ilmiy yangilik ayol yozuvchilar va yozuvchilarda erkak "men" ni yaratish fenomenining etarli darajada o'rganilmaganligi bilan belgilanadi. erkak yozuvchilardagi ayol "men". Asarda quyidagi xulosa chiqariladi: ijodkor ayolga munosabat ko'pincha salbiy bo'lganligi

sababli, yozuvchilar uchun chiqish yo'llaridan biri erkak niqobi orqasiga yashirinish edi. Biroq, ayol hali ham o'zining "ayollik intonatsiyasini" saqlab qoldi, bu "ayol matni" ning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarida namoyon bo'ldi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijod, intonatsiya, janr, adabiy tartibsizlik, feminizm.

Introduction

Virginia Woolf, construction, gender mask, women's literature, pseudonym, gender studies. In the last decades of the 20th century, the issue of "women's writing" turned into a subject of heated discussion in literary criticism, primarily after the activation of the "second wave" of feminism in the 1960s.

Since the middle of the XX century. women writers began to actively enter the literary arena ("women's voices in culture began to sound quite loudly only from the 20th century", and a separate phenomenon of "women's literature" appeared. "Women's studies" are now very actively engaged . .A. Zherebkin , E. I. Trofimov, S. Yu. Vorobyov, T. A. Rovenskaya, among Westerners - V. Wolf, M. Le Deff , K. Buttersby , M. Homans , E. Lauter , J. Fetherley , T. de Lauretis , G. Spivak , H. Baba, and others.

Since there is an ambiguous attitude towards the woman-creator in society, before talking about the specifics of women's creativity, it is necessary to understand the cultural-historical context in which the "creative woman" appeared. The psychology and philosophy of creativity in modern science is given very close attention. In philosophy, creativity is defined as an integral part of human existence, as something that brings a person closer to God. A number of scientists develop the ideas of N.A. Berdyaev about the role of creativity in life in general, arguing that "creative impulses accompany the entire history of man" and "creativity is the only true vocation of man, a metaphysical task".

However, there has been a very negative attitude towards a woman as a "creator" for many centuries. A woman was not in a hurry to be perceived as a creative subject, in every possible way leveling her success in the literary field and

in the field of art. Thus, for a long time the term "women's literature" was synonymous with low-grade literature that did not have the categories of taste and quality. Examples of such an attitude towards women's creativity will be highlighted in the relevant section of the article, and their own definition of the term "women's literature" will be proposed, since, in the author's opinion, the existing definitions need to be adjusted.

Already in the Middle Ages, misogyny actively developed, it even found its reflection in literature and in various forms of art. For example, in the scene of the Last Judgment in the Church of San Lazar in Autun (XII century), only two women are sent to Paradise, four to Hell. If in antiquity a woman had a number of rights, then during the period when the Carolingians came to power (715), women begin to lose their rights, their activities are sharply reduced, the space of women's life is limited only to the house and monastery.

Therefore, already in the Middle Ages, it was difficult for a woman to realize herself creatively - she was not recognized as a creator. Up until the 19th century, only sporadic examples are known of both women writers (K. Pisa - the author of the "Book of the City of Women", preachers Brigitte of Sweden and Catherine of Siena, petrakists : V. Colonna, V. Franco, G. Stampa and some others), and women -artists (A. Gentileschi).

Only by the 19th century the woman is gradually entering a more open creative path. Researchers attribute this fact to the emergence of feminism. By the 20th century In the US and the UK, feminism already occupies a very strong position in the public consciousness, so the work of many writers is studied precisely from the point of view of their commitment to feminism. So, for example, in a feminist vein, the prose of the American writer Ayn Rand is being explored.

Discussion and results

It should be noted that not everything written by a woman's hand automatically falls under the definition of "women's literature". A number of critics highlight this type of women's prose, which contains features of non-gender literature. Literature written by a female hand, but not positioning itself as "female", that is, "male discourse" appears in it, is considered extra-gender. According to Russian researcher M. Zavyalova, this type of writing is inherent in many Russian writers. In particular, about Irina Polyanskaya, she writes that she "recreates a male letter, where all sorts of questions of female identity and female nature are diligently avoided."

The Russian poetess and literary theorist Zinaida Gippius openly urged women writers to give up their gender, she advocated non-gender literature and a mixture of male and female principles in creativity. "If a human woman, after all, sometimes speaks, thinks and develops, this masculine principle intervened in her creates".

Typical genres of women's literature of high-quality, recognized as "high" women's literature are a novel (not love, but historical, biographical, autobiographical) and other forms of autobiographical writing in the first person (diary), as well as various "small genres" (story, novel, novella).

Although at the beginning of the 20th century from the lips of the great Russian poetess M. Tsvetaeva the following words were heard: "women still write about love and passion", it should be noted that many women writers of the 20th century. concerned about completely different topics - socio-political, history, art, the position of women in society and others. In this case, the center of the female narrative is always a woman. Thus, according to V. Wolf, "women write on various topics that even the previous generation would not have dared to touch. And today: poetry, and plays, and criticism, historical, biographical books, descriptions of travel and research, there are even several works on philosophy, natural sciences, and economics. And although novels still prevail, they have

probably also changed in collaboration with other genres. The first angularity and the epic age of female creativity are probably over. Thanks to reading and criticism, a greater breadth and thoughtfulness appeared.

Conclusion

Women's literature most often tells about sore issues: “telling about a problem” for women writers becomes synonymous with “solving a problem”. “Despair is the hidden face of modern women's prose, despair rooted in maternal instinct, love and concern for the ecology of the world of human relations, the fate and safety of loved ones, families, children.”

In the works of women's literature, there is no idealization of the image of a woman - on the contrary, the heroine is drawn through an accurate reproduction of reality, the life of a woman.

So, although women have been engaged in various types of creativity for many centuries (arts and crafts, embroidery, etc.), this activity was not perceived as something serious, but rather as a “secondary”. When a woman gained access to education, acquired political and social rights, and stood on the same level as a man in many issues (taken as a “neutral norm”), her work continued to be perceived as a “subculture” for a long time anyway.

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